

KANDUKURI VEERESALINGAM: THE PIONEER OF TRANSLATION STUDIES IN TELUGU

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Introduction:

It is a known fact that no language or literature can survive for a long time or come into fame without looking at the area of translations. It is by welcoming the famous works of other languages into it, and allowing the translations of its own into other languages – a language or literature can prove its mettle and get laurels. Translation studies – as an important area of literature has gained its name and fame in the recent decades. However, the seeds of Translation studies in Telugu have been laid by almost a century ago – by Sri Kandukuri Veeresalingam Panthulu.

The Two Yugakarthas:

It is a well known fact that the present day modern Telugu literature –owes a lot to the contributions made by the two great personalities of modern era - who are called **Yugakarthas** – namely, Sri Kandukuri Veeresalingam Panthulu, and Sri Gurajada Apparao. Among these two, the former personality i.e., Kandukuri garu had made an indelible mark on the Modern Telugu literature particularly, the prose form – across the genres – novel, short stories, Prose dramas, Journal articles and social essays. Perhaps there was no variety of prose that was not touched by Sri Kandukuri. That was the reason why he was called ‘Gadya Tikkana’ in Telugu literature. A unique feature of Kandukuri was that – he was not a mute preacher of social reforms, but an active practitioner which adds value to his written works.

Kandukuri: Modern Star of Telugu Renaissance:

When the Telugu society was suffering from its superstitions, and innumerable social evils, Kandukuri became the pioneer of reforms – social as well as literary. Kandukuri effectively used his literary skill to spread awareness on social evils and reform the society. He used different mediums such as – News papers, journals, magazines, stories, dramas, novels, etc. For his pioneering service, Kandukuri was fondly called the 'Modern Star of Telugu Renaissance'. He used his pen as a weapon to dispel the darkness of superstition and social vices. He heralded the dawn of a new era and marked a new awakening.

Kandukuri's Contributions to Telugu Literature:

Kandukuri's contribution to Telugu literature is two-fold. He was not only a great writer, but a reformer of the style. He can be considered as the bridge between the old ornate style and the common man's language.

Kandukuri was born in an age when simple and lucid style was anathema even for newspapers and periodicals. High-sounding language was considered the hallmark of the quality of writing. Veerasalingam proved that he was capable of performing all the time-honoured poetic feats and of exploding the bombast of prose. But, after establishing himself as a traditional writer, he slowly brought change in his style and demonstrated to the world the importance of simple, lucid, and straightforward language. He was the first to write a Telugu novel, Telugu drama, books on natural sciences and history in Telugu, and Telugu prose for women.

Pioneer of Translations into Telugu:

Kandukuri has influenced the modern Telugu Literature not only with his original works, but also with valuable and remarkable translations – mainly from Sanskrit and English. He brought the

invaluable treasures of Sanskrit literature and English literature to the reach of the common Telugu reader with his translations.

(i) Contribution for Scientific Writing:

Unlike his contemporaries, Veeresalingam wrote on scientific subjects like Physiology, Zoology and Astronomy in a style intelligible to the common reader. With his translations from English, Veeresalingam gave Telugu an elevated status. At a time when English was predominant for scientific writings, he developed the latent power of Telugu for Scientific expression. He pioneered coining Technical terminology in Telugu.

(ii) Contribution for General Literature:

Kandukuri's contribution to the general literature of Telugu is immense. Influenced by the English and other European literatures, Kandukuri gifted different literary forms to the Telugu Literature. Essays, novels, biographies, dramas, farces and satires were all his gift to Telugu. His autobiography (Sweeyacharita) was the first autobiography in Telugu and his Rajasekhara Charita, the first novel in Telugu. This is said to have been influenced by the English novel 'The Vicar of Wakefield' written by Oliver Goldsmith. This novel was translated into English under the title, **Fortune's Wheel**. He wrote a **Telugu grammar** on modern lines and a series of graded readers for school children influenced by the English Grammar books.

Kandukuri explained that he had started translating Oliver Goldsmith's *The Vicar of Wakefield* but because he thought a foreign story may not interest Telugu readers, he adapted it instead for writing a novel he titled *Rajasekhara Charitramu* (The Story of Rajasekhara) (1878). Among other reasons, Kandukuri's objective was to counter superstitions in Telugu society. *Rajasekhara Charitramu* was once again translated into English as *The Fortune's Wheel* (1887) and published in London.

Veeresalingam was the first person to introduce **Journal writing** into Telugu literature. Influenced by the English journals – on society and literature, and other essayists in Bengal, Veeresalingam **edited** and published many **journals**. With his journal articles, he used his pen as a weapon for striking hard at social evils. He started *Vivekavardhini*, a monthly journal. to point out and criticize the defects in the society. He also maintained several other journals like *Chintamani*, *Sateehitabodha*, *Satyasavardhani*, *Satyavadi* etc., and helped develop the Telugu literature and reformation of the society.

Veeresalingam was perhaps the first pathfinder in the field of research. His **History of Telugu Poets** was a monumental work, which involved tremendous labour, patience and perseverance. This was influenced by the Biographies produced on English writers in 18th and 19th centuries.

Veeresalingam was very much influenced by the satire dramas written by the English dramatists. He ridiculed the opponents of women's education in many satires, lampoons and drama like "*Brahma Vivaham*." Through his writings he criticized early marriages, *Kanyasulkam* (price of bride) and marriages of old men with young girls.

Kandukuri's Satyaraja Poorvadesayatralu (Satyaraja's Travel to the Distant Lands) was a satire on the contemporary male chauvinistic world. This novel pleads for a better treatment of upper-caste Indian women.

He also translated Goldsmith's poem "The Traveller" into Telugu as "Pathtika Vilasam" (1892) and William Cowper's John Gilpin (1875). It is not only fiction, drama, and poetry that he brought from English to Telugu but also Thomas Henry Huxley's book on physiology. Kandukuri not only borrowed from the colonial literary tradition, for instance the genre of the novel, but also emphasized its importance.

Similarly, he tried to create the image of a modern woman based on the model of British women. For example, his autobiography Satyasanjeevani (1887) (The Rejuvenator Called Truth) was meant for a women readership. Importantly, he published a number of texts from English literature in his journal **Satihitabodhini** (The One That Preaches Good to the Wives) (1883), a journal intended for women's awareness. He also published **a collection of the life stories of "ideal women"** such as Joan of Arc, Mary Carpenter, Elizabeth Frye, and others. And he borrowed from Jonathan Swift's Gulliver's Travels for his Satyaraja Poorvadesayatralu (1891) (Satyaraja's Travel to the Distant Lands).

Kandukuri's Other famous Prose works:

Kandukuri considered literature as a source of fighting against social evils and hence, instituted revolutionary activities in his writing. Some of his works include:

- Vyavahara Dharmabodhini (A Primer of Legal Practice, 1880)
- Brahma Vivaham (A Brahman Wedding, 1880).
- He wrote many plays on the attitude of Brahmin priests and dubious ethics of people in power, such as
 - Prahlada (1885),
 - Satya Harischandra (1886),
 - Tiryag-Vidwan Mahasabha (The Assembly of Demented Scholars, 1889),
 - Maharanya Puradhipatyam (A Sovereign of the Forest Kingdom, 1889), and
 - Viveka Deepika (A Torch of Wisdom, 1880).

- He translated Malavikagnimitram (1885), Prabodhachandrodayam (1885-91), and Ratnavali (1880) from Sanskrit
- His translations influenced by the English literature are:
 - Many dramas of Shakespeare
 - and Chamatkara Ratnavali (Comedy of Errors, 1880),
 - Ragamanjari (Sheridan's Duenna, 1885), and
 - Kalyana Kalpavalli (Sheridan's The Rivals, 1894) from English.

As explained above, Kandukuri Veeresalingam, the morning star of Telugu Renaissance, played an instrumental role in enriching the Modern Telugu literature with his translations and original works influenced by the English and European literature. The later writers including poets took the inspiration from Kandukuri and followed the European styles and genres in creating an entirely new, modern Telugu literary resource. Therefore, Kandukuri Veeresalingam can be said as the pioneer of Translation studies in Telugu.

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